

MnCo₂O₄/MIL-53(Fe) nanocomposite catalyst: Fabrication and its application for the effective sonodegradation of organic dyes from water media

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Abstract

In this work, for the first time, MnCo₂O₄/MIL-53(Fe) metal organic framework as a magnetically separable nanocomposite catalyst was successfully fabricated through the ultrasonic-assisted solvothermal method. FESEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD, and VSM analyses were used to identify the as-fabricated nanocomposite. The sonocatalytic performance of MnCo₂O₄/MIL-53(Fe) was then carried out in the degradation of organic dyes, namely methylene blue (MB), rhodamine B (RhB) and methyl orange (MO) organic dyes from water media. Several analytical factors, including irradiation time, initial dye concentration, process type, catalyst dosage, H₂O₂ concentration, and organic dye type were studied to achieve the maximum sonocatalytic efficiency. According to the gained results, the MnCo₂O₄/MIL-53(Fe) sonocatalyst was incredibly able to degrade the organic dyes by the ultrasonic (US)/H₂O₂ system. As well, abundant •OH free radicals as the main reactive species during the sonodegradation process was detected, which may be responsible for the high sonodegradation rate on MnCo₂O₄/MIL-53(Fe) under US irradiation. In addition, the degradation efficiency decreased less than 6% after 4 sequential cycles. All experimental outcomes revealed that the sonocatalytic degradation of organic dyes by the MnCo₂O₄/MIL-53(Fe) nanocomposite catalyst was an advisable choice for removing the toxic organic sewages.

Keywords MnCo₂O₄/MIL-53(Fe), metal organic framework, nanocomposite, catalyst, organic dyes, sonodegradation.